

Theoretical and Applied Technological Science Review

Volume: 2 Issue: 1 Year: 2024

ISSN-2958-7824

Received: 9 January 2024

Revised: 20 February 2024

Accepted: 23 March 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.>

Article

The Future of Electronic Human Resources: Artificial Intelligence and Automation in Human Resource Functions in the Information Technology Sector

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ABSTRACT

Organizations are looking for ways to simplify processes and procedures in order to increase efficiency, effectiveness, and agility in the new digital world. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology allows machines to think like humans. It is a technology that allows actions to be performed based on previously obtained data. AI is quickly becoming the core of our era's innovation. AI as a technology develops new business models, having an influence across different HR functions. Human resources are one of the most critical responsibilities of any organization. It is a technology that may automate low-value HR operations, allowing attention to move to strategic ones. HR professionals may use AI-powered solutions to evaluate employee performance, identify areas for growth, and deliver customized feedback. Almost all HR decisions will be driven by AI. These solutions can also give real-time performance data to HR personnel, allowing them to make data-driven choices about promotions, training, and other HR-related issues. This research is based on the latest review of the literature. Secondary data is collected from India's top IT companies through websites. This research explores the applications, roles, benefits, challenges, and ethical considerations of these technologies in reshaping the HR landscape. AI in HR will increase employee productivity and assist HR professionals in improving the whole experience, beginning with the recruiting process and continuing until the team member is onboarded and beyond. AI would assist in regaining time by automating low-value processes and focusing on business-driven initiatives.

Keywords: HRM, digital transformation, digital innovation, artificial intelligence, automation

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INTRODUCTION

The human resources function is essential to bridging the technological and human resource gaps in the era of Industry 4.0. The majority of the jobs that were formerly handled by human resources are now being replaced by technology, but the necessity for flexible HR services to handle the difficulties of managing people is still rising. Technology can assist in enhancing the HR process's agility in order to attain this flexibility. Being able to move swiftly and fluidly is a concept that is not new, and big businesses like Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon, and Microsoft have embraced it. Agility in the context of HR refers to the capacity to assist people, critical strategies, and organizational flexibility by allowing them to adjust and grow as persons and processes in response to quick and unanticipated changes.

In the rapidly advancing landscape of the IT sector, the future of electronic human resource management holds the promise of transformative change through the integration of artificial intelligence and automation. This evolution is poised to revolutionize HRM functions, ushering in unprecedented efficiency, strategic decision-making, and enhanced employee experiences. As organizations embrace cutting-edge technologies, the synergy of AI and automation is expected to redefine how HR processes operate, ultimately shaping the future of workforce management in the IT industry. The challenge of AI and automation in HR is the lack of human interaction and emotional intelligence.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Saraswathi, T., Karthikeyan, M., Balakrishnan, C., Nithya, T., Maheswari, B., & Subramanian, R., S. (2023). "Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management: Advancements, Implications, and Future Prospects", shows that artificial intelligence has the capacity to dramatically transform a number of aspects of human resource management. Examining how various HR procedures use AI-powered tools and platforms. These include hiring, performance

management, employee engagement, and learning and development. The use of AI and machine learning techniques to deliver meaningful data to support decision-making, automate routine HR tasks, and analyze enormous volumes of employee data. The future possibilities of AI in HRM are reviewed, along with the potential benefits and innovations that AI may bring to HRM practices. Sentiment analysis, predictive analytics, intelligent decision support, and customized employee experiences are all highlighted as novel uses of AI in HRM. The article emphasizes the importance of data infrastructure, data governance frameworks, and data-driven culture in order to fully realize the potential of AI in HRM. Overall, a thorough analysis of the challenges, opportunities, and state of play for AI in HRM. It compiles existing data, highlights areas in need of further study, and offers academics and practitioners fresh insights on how AI will radically transform HRM operations in the future.

Umasankar, A. Murugesan, Padmavathy Subramanian, Shefali Srivastava, and Ashish Dwivedi (2023) "A Study of Artificial Intelligence Impacts on Human Resource Digitalization in Industry 4.0", Robotics innovation, which encompasses both AI and the IoT, has brought up enormous prospects in the workplace thanks to AI. Industry 4.0 is thought to offer possible advantages in precision, efficiency, and flexibility. Numerous adjustments are necessary for Industry 4.0 deployment, including the HR department. The HR department's skill is increasingly important in Industry 4.0 and offers the company the upper hand. In order to respond to the challenges and demands, HR should be more circumspect and flexible. We research AI's contributions to Industry 4.0 HR practices and digitization. 271 HR professionals with backgrounds in IT, manufacturing, and administration were chosen to take part in this evaluation, which focused on three components of HR readiness and five AI applications in HR capabilities. The SPSS tool and the analysis of AMOS were used to review the data that had been gathered. The findings showed that studying hierarchical organizations is

essential to achieving sustainable development. All five of the AI application areas of HR support both human asset capabilities and adaptability. Improvements in safety and well-being were seen as essential elements of the AI application in HR.

Palos-Sánchez, P.R. Baena-Luna, P. Badicu A., and Infante-Moro J.C. (2022), "Artificial Intelligence and Human Resources Management: A Bibliometric Analysis", the use of artificial intelligence in businesses is growing. AI has been more and more applicable in the field of human resource management in recent years. The objective of this article is to conduct a bibliometric study of the scientific literature that discusses the use and implications of AI in the field of human resource management in a linked manner. Web of Science and Scopus were the scientific databases searched; they produced a total of 156 articles at first, of which 73 were chosen for further examination. The findings demonstrate that AI applied to HRM is a rapidly expanding field of study with a promising future. However, it should be noted that the field is highly specialized because the majority of research focuses on using AI in recruitment and selection processes, ignoring other subfields with significant application potential.

Verma, Richa, and Bandi, Srinivas (2019), "Artificial Intelligence and Human Resource Management in the Indian IT Sector", this article discusses how the evolving IT landscape has led to advances in technology and the application of AI in human resources. Artificial intelligence is being used by almost all businesses in the IT sector to improve the productivity of their human resources. The effort starts with an automated hiring procedure and continues with employee performance reviews. Executives in charge of organizations and human resources are certain that integrating AI into HR tasks like benefit administration and onboarding would enhance the overall work experience. They explained in this article how individuals see artificial

intelligence as a benefit and a danger to their jobs. I examined a few of the leading artificial intelligence businesses as a point of comparison. Concentrated on the difficulties and constraints that artificial intelligence faces in the current business environment.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the concept of electronic HRM in the information technology sector
- To study the various applications, challenges, and ethical considerations of the IT sector.
- Identifying the benefits of HR digitization in the IT sector.
- To study the top IT companies in India
- To provide employees with more personalized, tailored career growth opportunities and improve employee engagement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study primarily relied on secondary data as there was no primary research conducted. The research study is using a descriptive research design. The secondary data has been collected from research papers, publications, websites, HR blogs, and survey reports published by various research organizations. Electronic HRM: Artificial Intelligence and Automation in the IT Sector

The integration of electronic human resource management with artificial intelligence and automation in the IT sector represents a paradigm shift in how HR functions are executed and optimized. Here are key aspects of EHRM in the context of AI and automation in the IT sector:

Recruitment Transformation: AI algorithms streamline and enhance the recruitment process, automating candidate sourcing, screening, and

matching. This ensures a more efficient and precise selection of talent in the competitive IT job market.

Predictive Analytics for Workforce Planning: AI-driven predictive analytics enable organizations to forecast workforce needs, identify potential skills gaps, and strategize talent management initiatives to meet the evolving demands of the IT sector.

Personalized Employee Experiences: Automation and AI technologies tailor employee experiences, from onboarding to ongoing development. Personalization fosters engagement and satisfaction, contributing to a positive work culture in the dynamic IT work environment.

Skills Development and Training: AI identifies skill gaps and recommends personalized training programmes, ensuring that employees stay relevant in the rapidly evolving IT landscape. This facilitates continuous learning and development.

Efficiency in HR Processes: Automation streamlines routine HR tasks, freeing up time for HR professionals to focus on strategic initiatives. This efficiency contributes to agility and adaptability in managing the dynamic needs of the IT workforce.

Data-Driven Decision-Making: AI analytics provide actionable insights from HR data, empowering decision-makers to make informed choices related to talent acquisition, performance management, and overall HR strategy in the IT sector.

Ethical Considerations: As AI plays a central role, ethical considerations become crucial. Ensuring fairness, transparency, and data privacy in AI-driven HR processes is imperative to build trust and maintain ethical practices.

Remote Work Enablement: e-HRM, combined with AI and automation, facilitates the management of remote teams by providing tools for virtual

collaboration, performance monitoring, and employee well-being support in the IT sector.

Cybersecurity in HR Data: With the increasing reliance on AI, safeguarding sensitive HR data is paramount. Robust cybersecurity measures are essential to protect against potential breaches and ensure the integrity of employee information.

Continuous Technological Adaptation: e-HRM systems need to be adaptive to emerging technologies. Integrating with new tools and platforms allows HR professionals in the IT sector to stay ahead in a rapidly changing technological landscape.

In summary, the fusion of e-HRM with AI and automation in the IT sector signifies a transformative era where technology augments HR capabilities, enhances employee experiences, and contributes to the overall agility and competitiveness of organizations in the tech industry.

The Future of Electronic Human Resource Management in the IT Sector

The future of e-HRM in the IT sector is poised for a profound transformation with the integration of artificial intelligence and automation. This evolution is driven by a range of advancements that promise to reshape HR functions and redefine the relationship between technology and human resource management.

Efficiency Revolution: AI and automation will revolutionize HR processes, streamlining tasks such as recruitment, onboarding, and performance management. This efficiency will allow HR professionals in the IT sector to focus on strategic initiatives and high-value activities.

Data-Driven Decision-Making: The integration of AI will enable HR teams to harness the power of data analytics for more informed decision-making. Predictive analytics will play a crucial role in

workforce planning, talent management, and identifying trends within the IT workforce.

Personalised Employee Experiences: Automation will facilitate the delivery of personalized experiences for employees. From onboarding to professional development, AI-driven systems will adapt to individual needs, contributing to higher job satisfaction and retention rates in the IT industry.

Recruitment Transformation: AI algorithms will revolutionize the recruitment process by analyzing vast datasets to identify the most suitable candidates. This will result in more accurate and efficient hiring processes, addressing the dynamic talent needs of the rapidly evolving IT sector.

Continuous Learning and Upskilling: AI will play a pivotal role in identifying skills gaps within the IT workforce. Personalised learning paths and upskilling programmes will ensure that employees remain competitive in the face of technological advancements.

Ethical Considerations: As AI becomes more integrated into HRM, ethical considerations will become increasingly important. Ensuring fairness, transparency, and data privacy will be paramount to maintaining trust and ethical practices within the IT sector.

Adaptability to Emerging Technologies: EHRM systems will need to demonstrate a high degree of adaptability to keep pace with emerging technologies. Integrating with new tools and platforms will be crucial to staying ahead in the dynamic IT landscape.

Employee Well-being Focus: AI applications will extend beyond operational tasks to monitor and support employee well-being. Proactive measures, such as stress detection and wellness programmes, will contribute to a healthier and more resilient IT workforce.

Human-Tech Collaboration: Striking the right balance between technology and the human touch will be essential. While AI and automation enhance efficiency, human empathy and understanding will remain critical in HR interactions within the IT sector.

Global Talent Management: The integration of AI will enable more effective global talent management. HR professionals in the IT sector can leverage technology to navigate diverse cultural landscapes and manage talent across borders seamlessly.

In essence, the future of e-HRM in the IT sector is a dynamic landscape where AI and automation serve as enablers, empowering HR professionals to navigate challenges, foster innovation, and create a workplace that aligns with the evolving demands of the tech-driven industry.

THE FUTURE OF HR: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HUMAN RESOURCES

Artificial intelligence is a technology that enables systems to think like humans. It is a technology that allows performing tasks based on previously collected data. Artificial intelligence is soon to become the foundation of innovation in this era. The term AI is often interchangeably used with machine learning and deep learning; however, there are differences. Machine learning is an AI; however, all AI is not machine learning. Most companies have started using AI to improve performance and productivity by automating tasks. AI as technology defines new ways of operating the business, creating an impact across multiple functions. Human resources are one of the most important functions of the organization, especially in the age of great resignation. Directly associated with the team members working in the organization, this is where AI as a technology is defining new ways to operate the business. It is a tool

that can be utilized to automate low-value HR functions so that the focus is shifted toward strategic ones.

APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HR FUNCTIONS

Talent Acquisition: The foundation of the HR department is talent acquisition, which is the process of adding new members to the team to potentially develop and expand the company. Efficient hiring is crucial for today's businesses. AI may be applied in the hiring process in several ways, including by creating simple forms for candidates to fill out, filtering applications first based on factors like experience, education, and willingness to move and keeping up the complete applicant database. Examine the individuals who are currently in the pool and determine which ones are qualified for the newly available post. When setting up interviews, AI-driven chatbots may be used to locate and get in touch with possible prospects. By employing these strategies, recruiting would take considerably less time and be completed more quickly, freeing up the HR staff to concentrate on other important duties that would raise productivity within the company.

Onboarding: Since onboarding is the first encounter a new hire has with the company, it is one of the most important procedures. The members of the crew will never forget that impression. AI may assist HR in streamlining the onboarding process in some ways, including AI-consolidated technologies that will make it easier for new hires to comprehend the organization's values, business culture, and other pertinent information. AI will assist in automating administrative tasks like creating logins and filling out forms. Artificial intelligence (AI)-powered digital assistants may streamline the onboarding procedure from start to finish by proactively recommending the

next actions to the new team member, allowing the process to ramp up swiftly. It can suggest to new hires any learning programme that fits their skill set until the new hire's assigned assignment is finished.

Team member experience: Artificial intelligence technology may assist with some activities related to employee engagement, such as employee recognition programmes, real-time feedback, and personalized feedback surveys. These programmes enable HR to assess team members' engagement and/or satisfaction with greater accuracy than in the past. By using these programmes, HR may even identify team members who are most likely to leave, which enables the HR department to proactively implement retention tactics and lower turnover. Using AI-driven chatbot to provide team members responses in real time can improve the team members' experience. Colleagues only need to type their questions, and the chatbot will provide the solution.

Career Development: Career development is one of the most important variables in career retention, which is a strategic strategy that organizations should utilize in the present uncertain market. Diverse learning and development opportunities that benefit both the team members and the organization should be made available to team members. Here are some examples of how AI might support team members' professional growth: Artificial intelligence software can suggest tailored training to team members who need it. This will improve team member morale. AI is able to gather performance data for every team member. If there are any specific skill shortages, these can be found by reviewing this data. In these situations, team members can receive clarification, and training or educational initiatives can be recommended based on the information provided. This will therefore promote team learning. Given the aforementioned, AI in HR will increase worker productivity and assist HR professionals in enhancing the entire experience, beginning with the hiring

procedure and continuing through the onboarding of new team members. By automating low-value operations and concentrating on business-driven initiatives, artificial intelligence can help recover time.

BENEFITS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AUTOMATION IN THE IT SECTOR

Automation of routine HR tasks and processes through AI leads to increased efficiency, allowing HR professionals in the IT sector to focus on strategic initiatives and high-value activities. AI-driven analytics provide HR teams with data-driven insights, enabling more informed and strategic decision-making in talent management, workforce planning, and overall HR functions. Automation reduces manual workloads, leading to cost savings for organizations in the IT sector. This includes savings on time, resources, and potential errors associated with manual HR processes. AI in recruitment processes enhances accuracy in candidate selection by analyzing data beyond traditional parameters. This results in more precise matches between job requirements and candidate skills in the IT industry. AI applications can tailor HR interactions and interventions, creating personalized experiences for employees in the IT sector, thereby contributing to increased job satisfaction and engagement. Automation expedites the onboarding process, ensuring that new hires in the IT sector can quickly integrate into their roles, access necessary information, and contribute effectively to the organization. Predictive analytics powered by AI enable HR teams to proactively identify and address talent gaps, ensuring that the IT sector has the right skills and capacities to meet future demands. AI-driven training programmes can adapt to individual learning styles and preferences, promoting continuous learning and development for employees in the dynamic field of IT. AI supports more accurate

workforce planning by analyzing historical data and predicting future talent needs, helping organizations in the IT sector align their workforce with business goals. AI can assist in monitoring and ensuring compliance with HR regulations and data protection laws, reducing the risk of legal issues, and ensuring a secure and compliant HR environment in the IT industry.

CHALLENGES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AUTOMATION IN THE IT SECTOR

Resistance to Change: Employees and HR professionals may resist the adoption of AI and automation due to fear of job displacement or unfamiliarity with new technologies.

Data Security Concerns: The increased reliance on AI and automation in e-HRM raises concerns about the security and privacy of sensitive employee data.

Algorithmic Bias: AI systems may exhibit bias if trained on biased datasets, potentially leading to discriminatory HR decisions. Addressing algorithmic bias and ensuring fairness in AI-driven processes is a significant challenge.

Skill Gaps: The rapid evolution of technology may result in skill gaps among HR professionals who may lack the necessary expertise to manage and optimize AI and automation tools effectively.

Integration Challenges: Integrating AI and automation into existing HRM systems can be complex and may require significant investments in technology infrastructure. Ensuring seamless integration and interoperability is a key challenge.

Ethical Dilemmas: The use of AI in HRM raises ethical questions, such as the ethical handling of employee data, the impact on job satisfaction, and the ethical

use of AI in decision-making processes. Establishing ethical guidelines is essential.

Regulatory Compliance: Keeping up with evolving regulations regarding AI and automation in HRM poses a challenge. Adhering to legal requirements and ensuring that AI applications comply with industry standards is crucial.

Overreliance on Technology: Excessive dependence on AI and automation may lead to a loss of the human touch in HR processes. Balancing technology with human involvement to maintain empathy and personal connections is a challenge.

Cost of Implementation: Initial investments in AI and automation technologies can be high. Ensuring a positive return on investment and managing costs effectively are challenges organizations may face.

Continuous Learning: The field of AI is dynamic, and staying abreast of the latest advancements requires continuous learning for HR professionals. Providing ongoing training and development opportunities is essential to keeping HR teams updated and proficient in utilising emerging technologies.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AUTOMATION IN THE IT SECTOR

Algorithmic Bias: Ethical considerations arise from the potential bias embedded in AI algorithms. HRM systems must be designed and monitored to ensure fairness and avoid discrimination, especially in areas like recruitment and performance evaluation.

Privacy Concerns: The use of AI in e-HRM involves handling vast amounts of personal data. Ethical practices demand robust privacy measures to protect employee information, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations in the IT sector.

Informed Consent: Ethical e-HRM practices involve obtaining informed consent from employees regarding the collection, processing, and use of their data. This transparency helps build trust and ensures that employees are aware of how AI is impacting HR functions.

Employee Autonomy: Balancing the use of AI with employee autonomy is crucial. Employees should have control over their personal data and be informed about how AI is influencing HR decisions that affect them in the IT sector.

Job Displacement and Reskilling: Ethical considerations surround the potential impact of AI and automation on jobs. Organizations must adopt responsible practices, including reskilling programmes, to mitigate negative consequences such as job displacement in the IT industry.

Security Measures: Ethical e-HRM practices require robust cybersecurity measures to safeguard AI systems and the sensitive HR data they handle. This includes protecting against potential breaches and unauthorized access to employee information.

Fairness in Opportunities: AI tools should be designed to promote fairness in providing opportunities and benefits within the workforce. Monitoring and addressing any unintended biases in decision-making processes ensure equal opportunities for employees in the IT sector.

Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Ethical considerations extend to the ongoing monitoring and evaluation of AI systems. Regular assessments are necessary to identify and rectify any ethical issues that may arise as technology evolves in the HRM function.

Open Communication: Establishing open communication channels between HR professionals, IT teams, and employees is vital for addressing ethical concerns. Encouraging dialogue and feedback ensures

that ethical considerations remain a priority in the evolving landscape of e-HRM in the IT sector.

THE TOP IT COMPANIES IN INDIA

Tata Consultancy Services (TCS): TCS is one of the largest IT services and consulting companies in India, providing a wide range of services globally.

Infosys: Infosys is a multinational corporation that offers business consulting, information technology, and outsourcing services. It is known for its global presence and technological expertise.

Wipro: Wipro is a global IT company that provides services such as IT consulting, system integration, and business process outsourcing.

HCL Technologies: HCL is an Indian multinational IT services and consulting company, offering a range of services including IT consulting, enterprise transformation, and engineering services.

Tech Mahindra: Tech Mahindra is a part of the Mahindra Group and offers IT services, business process outsourcing, and consulting services to clients across various industries. Regarding e-HRM, AI, and automation in these companies, it's important to note that specific initiatives and implementations can vary. Generally, major IT firms are actively incorporating AI and automation into their operations, including HR functions, to enhance efficiency, talent management, and overall organizational performance. These companies leverage AI for talent acquisition, employee engagement, data-driven decision-making, and automation for routine HR tasks. The integration of these technologies into EHRM aligns with global trends to create more agile and responsive HR processes, contributing to the effectiveness of workforce management. For the most current and

detailed information on specific initiatives, it's recommended to refer to the latest reports, press releases, or official communications from each company.

CONCLUSION

The integration of artificial intelligence and automation into electronic human resource management marks a transformative chapter for HR functions in the IT sector. The objectives set for this future landscape encompass efficiency enhancement, strategic decision-making, and a profound focus on employee experiences. As organizations in the IT industry navigate this evolution, the promise of optimized recruitment, skills development, and compliance management through AI is evident. However, challenges such as ethical considerations, algorithmic bias, and the need for ongoing skill development must be addressed diligently. The benefits, including increased efficiency, cost optimization, and enhanced employee experiences, present a compelling case for the continued integration of AI and automation. Striking a balance between technological advancements and ethical considerations, fostering adaptability, and ensuring employee well-being will be pivotal for organizations to thrive in this dynamic future of EHRM within the IT sector. In essence, the strategic adoption of AI and automation stands poised to reshape HR functions, empowering professionals in the IT sector to navigate the complexities of talent management and workforce optimization in an ever-evolving technological landscape.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

M. K. Ganeshan is a recipient of the Indian Council of Social Science Research Doctoral Fellowship. His article is largely an outcome of his doctoral work sponsored by ICSSR. However, the author is entirely responsible for the facts stated, the opinions expressed, and the conclusions drawn.

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